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Atentamente,
el equipo DACIU.

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EFFECTS OF THE ORBIT ORIENTATION ON THE EVOLUTION OF DWARF SATELLITE GALAXIES

Paula España Fontán
M. Ángeles Gómez Flechoso

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Abstract

Cosmological models propose a hierarchical scenario for the evolution of the galaxies, where dwarf galaxies are accreted in the halo of larger ones, known as host or main galaxies. Observations of galaxy systems indicate that the distribution of satellite dwarf galaxies in the main galaxy halo is not homogeneous, but presents a planar distribution perpendicular to the disk of the main galaxy. In this work, we analyze a possible origin of this inhomogeneous distribution due to different survival times of the satellites depending on the orientation of their orbits.

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1. Introduction

The current cosmological model for structure formation in the Universe is based on the standard cold dark matter theory with cosmological constant Λ (Λ CDM), which sets an scenario where dark matter (DM) haloes form first, and grow hierarchically from the initial matter density perturbations, through subsequent mergers and accretion (e.g. [1], [2], [3], [5]). Simultaneously, gas cools and collapses into the potential well of these DM haloes, leading to the process of star formation, and origination of the first protogalaxies, which will follow the same mergers as their DM haloes. Before being accreted by the central object, satellite galaxies orbit around them for a varying amount of time, depending on the mass ratio, while experiencing a progressive mass-loss, that affects both its DM and stellar component (e.g. [6], [7], [8], [9]). We find proof of this in the discovered complex stellar structures (shells and streams), that are created through processes of accretion and tidal disruption of satellite galaxies. This can be observed in our own Galaxy (e.g. [10], [11], [12], [13], [14], [15], [16]), in the Andromeda galaxy ([17], [18], [19]), and beyond the Local Group (e.g. [20], [21], [22], [23])

With respect to the configuration of the falling process, we shall point out that the Copernican principle dictates that the universe, at large, is homogeneous and isotropic. Even certain numerical simulations of standard Λ CDM model predict homogeneity of the infalling directions of satellites. Yet it has been noticed that satellites show preferential orbit planes, the trend being an alignment perpendicular to the disk. Indeed, it has long been evident in the Milky Way (MW) (see [24] and [25]), and first quantified by [26] with the 11 "classical" (brightest) satellites, which appear forming a common planar structure, roughly perpendicular to the Galactic disk (despite the obscuration from the Galactic disk, that complicates the study of this planar structure, see [27]). Moreover, observational studies from the last decade showed that additional streams, globular clusters, and newly discovered fainter satellites (see SDSS; [28]), contributed further to the anisotropy, building the so-called "VPOS" for "vast polar structure" around the MW (e.g. [29], [30], [31]).

This anisotropic nature has also been confirmed around the M31 galaxy (e.g. [32], [33], [34]), where two similar and nearly perpendicular planes of satellites have been found: the so-called "GPoA" or "Great Plane of Andromeda" with 19 members (see [30], [31]), and the "Ibata-Conn-14" plane (see [35], [36]), noted with the Pan-Andromeda Archaeological Survey or PAndAS. Finally, there have been recent discoveries of star clusters and dwarf galaxies suggesting flattened and irregular distribution in other nearby galactic systems in the local universe, such as Cen A (see e.g. [37], [38], and [39]), M81 [40], M101 [41] and NGC 253 [42]. Nonetheless, we shall point out the difficulty of positional data analysis for satellite galaxies, caused by the limitation to 2D projections in some cases (as it happens for example in Cen A). Basically M31 and the MW are the only galaxies for which 3D positions are available.

Theoretical studies have tried to assess the configuration of planar distribution of the satellite galaxies through cosmological simulations within the Λ CDM paradigm, due to the strong observational foundation that has been stated. There are different factors that could explain it; on the one hand, galaxies reside within a complex network of filaments and sheets, often called "The Cosmic Web" [4]; on the other hand, we must take into account local effects: to begin with, the presence of relatively massive dwarf satellites, can produce an asymmetric potential that affects the rest of the satellites [43]; secondly, the morphology of the satellite and of the central galaxy might be determining; last of all, disk central galaxies can accelerate tidal disruption

on certain orbits. This study focuses on the latter reason, and therefore we analyze the significance of the angle between the orbital plane and the central disk in the destruction of the satellite. We use N-body simulations to study the influence of the initial orientation on the process of accretion of satellite galaxies. We change the orbit of the satellite, adopting three several angles between the planar disk of the host galaxy and the orbital plane of the dwarf galaxy: 0° , 90° , and 45° , at halfway stage. We also employ two initial velocities for the satellite galaxy, to test different types of orbits.

The paper is organized as follows: Section 2 describes the numerical methods and the parameters we used, while the results obtained for different orbit parameters are reported in Section 3. Finally, Section 4 summarizes the results and exposes the conclusions reached, in a brief discussion.

2. Methods

The description of galaxy accretion deals with a broad parameter space, for it must include the orbital parameters of the merger process, and those that define the structure of the galaxies involved. In this paper, we concentrate on the first ones, while keeping the second ones fixed, since we pursue to examine the influence of the orbital orientation of the satellite, on stellar and DM mass removal. In order to do so, we will only study satellites accreted by isolated massive galaxies. In particular, we are dealing with a mass ratio of ~ 0.001 , so we shall assume without loss of generality, that satellites don't affect the dynamics of their hosts. Apart from that, we will disregard morphology effects, and keep fixed the structure and the mass of the galaxies, varying the initial position and kinetic energy of the satellite.

2.1. Initial conditions

In our simulations, we bear in mind DM and baryonic matter, including stars and gas. DM is taken into account for gravitational interactions (just as stars); morphology evolution and satellite disruption are evident following the stars trail; lastly, we include gas to incorporate hydrodynamical effects like dissipation. The morphologies we employ for each galaxy are: disk for the primary one, with a disk+bulge halo component; and a spheroidal satellite. Parameters of the host, such as mass, size-scales and shape, are characteristic of a MW-like galaxy. A detailed description of the model can be found in [44]. The satellite, on the other hand, follows a King model [45]. Basic properties are displayed in Tables 1 and 2.

TABLE 1: Properties of the host galaxy

Primary galaxy	
Total number of particles	45319
Number of baryonic particles	15671
Number of DM particles	29648
Baryonic mass [$10^{10} M_\odot$]	8.25
DM mass [$10^{10} M_\odot$]	24
Scale length of the exponential disk [kpc]	2.5
Total radius of the DM halo [kpc]	70

TABLE 2: Properties of the satellite galaxy

Satellite galaxy	
Total number of particles	10000
Typical radius [kpc]	0.3
Total mass [$10^{10} M_{\odot}$]	0.017

In all the simulations, satellites are initially released at a radius of 50 kpc from the primary galaxy, and null radial velocity. To explore different orbits, we establish two values for the initial tangential velocity. Finally, we set the parameter we will focus on, the angle between the disk of the central galaxy and the orbital plane. All the orbital parameters are reported in Table 3.

TABLE 3: Orbital parameters of the satellite galaxy

Model	Initial position (x, y, z) [kpc]	Initial velocity (v_x, v_y, v_z) [km/s]	Angle (θ) [degrees]
001	(0, 0, 50)	(0, 60, 0)	90
101	($25\sqrt{2}, 0, 25\sqrt{2}$)	(0, 60, 0)	45
100	(50, 0, 0)	(0, 60, 0)	0
002	(0, 0, 50)	(0, 120, 0)	90
202	($25\sqrt{2}, 0, 25\sqrt{2}$)	(0, 120, 0)	45
200	(50, 0, 0)	(0, 120, 0)	0

2.2. Numerical methods

Here we describe the procedures followed to find the satellite's highest density point along its orbit, and the time until its disruption. The simulations were run using a treecode algorithm [46] and the analysis of the satellite evolution was made using python programs.

To track the orbit, the morphology deformation, and the disruption process of the dwarf galaxy, we are interested in the density nucleus, rather than the center of mass (CM from now on). Therefore, we made iterated computations of the CM, reducing by a constant α the number of particles used in the calculation (the satellite core), as long as the distance between the positions of the CM in two successive iterations exceeded a parameter β . Then, we assumed that the satellite was totally disrupted when the core was reduced to less than 15 particles (which showed that the iterations started to diverge). The values of both parameters, α and β , are listed in Table 4. For the upcoming analysis, we will consider $\alpha = 1.015$ and $\beta = 0.7$ as the standard case; the remaining values are used to check the stability of our results under small perturbations of the parameters.

TABLE 4: Parameters α and β used in the numerical calculations

Parameters	Values		
α	1.015	1.025	
β	0.63	0.7	0.77

TABLE 5: Numerical results of the simulations with the standard parameters. For each satellite model, we find the number of orbits before disruption, the life time (or time of destruction), and the time and radius of the first pericenter.

Model	Number of orbits	Life time [10^6 years]	Time of the first pericenter [10^6 years]	Radius of the first pericenter [kpc]
001	4.923	3200.0	325.0	9.517
101	3.958	2375.0	300.0	10.279
100	2.208	1325.0	300.0	6.810
002	9.563	7650.0	400.0	24.422
202	9.300	6975.0	375.0	22.943
200	6.286	4400.0	350.0	19.555

3. Results

Below, we will examine the dependence of tidal stripping efficiency on the satellite's initial planar orbit orientation. Note that, on the one hand, we used the same model galaxies in all simulations, but on the other hand, we analyzed 3 different inclinations: orbit perpendicular to the disk ($\theta = 90^\circ$), coplanar with it ($\theta = 0^\circ$), and in between ($\theta = 45^\circ$). As expected, the lower θ , the higher the disruption efficiency, since the tidal stripping is the strongest for the coplanar orientation, and vice versa. We find that when the orbiting satellite approaches in a parallel plane, the destruction time is much shorter (between 1.5 and 2.5 times shorter) than the time taken when it approaches in a perpendicular plane (for the oblique plane, it is in between). These differences can already be appreciated in the beginning of the falling process. Indeed, the pericenter time and radius in the perpendicular orbit are around 10% and 33% higher (respectively) than in the parallel orbit. This is consistent with previous studies on the field [47].

To compare the different models, we scaled down the time life of each one (i.e, the time interval until the satellite is totally disrupted), with its own pericenter time (the time taken to reach a pericenter after the satellite is released), thus obtaining standard and dimensionless time measurements. This means we are basically comparing the fraction of orbits that the satellites manages to cover before being destroyed. However, we are also interested in the absolute times and distances recorded in the first pericenter, in order to detect premature effects.

Apart from this, we tested two different kinetic energies for the satellite (the second having twice the initial velocity of the first one), to compare the effects on orbits showing more radial or circular tendencies. Our results show that it takes more than twice the time to disrupt the more circular orbits (models 002, 202, and 200), compared to the more elliptical ones (models 001, 101, and 100). These results are in agreement with previous studies [48], asserting that a more radial (eccentric) accretion leads to a faster mass-loss.

The results of the satellite disruption for all the simulations were automatically stored through the python program, and are displayed in Table 5. Regarding the stability of the programs used, since we always find a faster destruction for a higher approximation to the primary plane (i.e, lower θ), no matter the values taken by the parameters from Table 4, we confirm that the results are reliable.

FIGURE 1: 3D representation of the host galaxy (blue), the satellite galaxy (red), and a translucent sphere that points out the boundary of the particles used to calculate the CM, after 1 Gigayears orbiting the host galaxy. From left to right, we observe the models 001, 101, 100 (first column); and 002, 202, 200 (second column).

Additionally, we plot the evolution of the stellar component of the main galaxy and dwarf galaxy in three-dimensional figures, during 1.325 Gigayears, that is, the lifetime of the shortest model (Fig. 1). In this plot, the differences in the satellite disruption and the appearance of tidal tails depending on the orbit are evident.¹

4. Discussion

In this work, we used N-body simulation to study how the angle between the initial orbital plane of the satellite and the central galaxy disk, and the ellipticity of the orbit affect the accretion process of the satellite galaxy. We kept all morphological

¹These are interactive images, and to visualize the moving images one needs a document reader that supports interactive pdfs (such as Acrobat Reader).

and structural parameters of the main galaxy fixed (stellar and DM mass, halo structure, etc.) while we experimented with the initial orbital orientation and velocity of the dwarf galaxy. To define the time taken for the satellite galaxy to be disintegrated, after suffering dispersion of its mass, because of tidal forces from the central halo, the convergence criteria of the CM calculation has been used. We used two parameters that characterized the stability and the accuracy of the iterative CM. By slight modifications of both parameters, we proved the robustness of our calculations for the destruction time.

We change the orbit of the satellite, adopting three different angles between the planar disk of the host galaxy and the orbital plane of the dwarf galaxy: 0° , 45° and 90° . Our results show that the satellite's approaching orientation to the host galaxy determines strongly the time taken for the satellite to be completely disrupted. Orbits parallel to the disk of the main galaxy produce faster tidal disruption of the satellite galaxy than perpendicular orbits.

Furthermore, we work with two initial velocities for the satellite galaxy (altering therefore the orbit and the kinetic energy), with the same initial radial distance, so that the initial potential energy remains invariant. In this way, we saw that the relation between the destruction time for the different angles also depends on the orbital structure and the initial velocity.

As would be expected, based on the observational background of tangentially biased orbits in satellite's populations, dwarf galaxies orbiting in a plane perpendicular to the disk experience a weaker mass-loss than those lying on the same plane. This can be explained through the wider contact between galaxies in the second case, which leads to more friction among baryonic matter, and makes it harder to retain matter close to the center. We have represented this result in Figure 2. Each model is depicted in a different color; the color code associates redness to an initial velocity of 120 km/s, and greenish tones to 60 km/h. Plus, in the darkness scale, lighter colors indicate lower perpendicularity to the central disk. The upper panel plots the evolution of the distance of the density core of the satellite to the center of the host galaxy, until it is totally disrupted. One can observe that all orbits with more circular tendency (reddish ones), survive for longer times. But more importantly, it reveals that the destruction of the satellite due to tidal stripping, is faster for orbits parallel to the central disk, since the time of destruction appears to be shorter.

The lower panel, on the other hand, shows how the satellite's apocenters are gradually reduced, as satellites end up accreted by the host. It also shows that tidal forces produce an effect of dilution that exceeds the orbital decay, which is derived from the fact that the time of total disruption (that determines the ending point of each graph), anticipates the process of decay, as the approachment of the satellite's nucleus to the host galaxy is not so sharp yet. As a result, disrupted stars will remain in the halo, not the disc or the bulge. We even observe slight fluctuations to higher distances, which can mistakenly lead to the thought of being in contradiction with the fact of the initial position being an apocenter, since it would imply an increase in the total energy. However, this further separation of the density peak with respect to the center of mass, can be explained through an approach of the tidal streams to the galaxy disk, so there is no contradiction at all. Therefore, the position of the CM (not the density nucleus, which is what is represented in Figure 2), would never exceed the initial distance to the disk.

Forthcoming research could be oriented to determining the relative significance of the different agents affecting asymmetry in the process of accreted satellites into

FIGURE 2: Evolution of the distance of the density core of the satellite to the center of the host galaxy (above panel); and apocenters of the orbit (that is, the point of the orbit furthest from the center of the host galaxy) as a function of the time, before the destruction of the satellite galaxy (lower panel).

the potential well of large galaxies, or even identifying the dominant factor². It would also be interesting to follow in more detail the destruction processes, focussing on tracking the particles. Further development of this project would also be profitable, varying largely the orbital parameters (e.g. including co-rotating and counter-rotating satellite galaxies). Another issue remaining is the evaluation of whether the ratio of orbits observed for each angle corresponds to the expected results, taking all known contributing factors into account. This way, one could check if our predictions are effective, and whether all aspects are enough to explain observational data, making a statistical analysis of the problem. Additionally, one could address the detailed effects of stellar stripping on galaxy formation and evolution.

²For example, [47] assures that the effect of the orbit orientation is sub-dominant with respect to the satellite morphology.

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